

Rate of changes of potassium and cationic micronutrients in submerged soil affected by potassium and zinc interactions

Priyama Roy*^a, Ajit Kumar Dolui^a, Mitali Mandal^b, Satyajit Sarkar^c and Dilip Kumar Das^a

^aDepartment of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Institute of Agricultural Science, University of Calcutta, 51/2, Hazra Road, Kolkata-700 019, India

E-mail : priyamaroy@gmail.com

^bCollege of Agriculture, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar-751 003, Odisha, India

^cWater Management Research Centre, Department of Agriculture, Ranaghat, Government of West Bengal, India

Manuscript received 08 April 2015, revised 24 June 2015, accepted 01 July 2015

Abstract : The interaction study between potassium and zinc was conducted with an inceptisol under submerged soil condition at ambient laboratory conditions with their nine different treatment combinations. It was found that exchangeable K increased gradually till 42 days of incubation before decreasing and was maintained highest (189.20 mg kg⁻¹) in the treatment T₆ where both K and Zn were applied combinedly at 60 and 5 mg kg⁻¹ respectively. But regarding changes with respect to the cationic micronutrients it was observed that the amount of Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn was highest with the values 152.94, 64.94, 2.64 and 10.18 mg kg⁻¹ respectively in the treatment T₉ where K and Zn were applied combinedly at their highest level (K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil and Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil) at 42 days of incubation for Fe and Mn, 35 days of incubation for Cu and 14 days of incubation for Zn. From the present investigation it is concluded that both Zn and K has a positive synergistic effect on one another under submerged soil conditions.

Keywords : Exchangeable K, inceptisol, interaction, positive synergistic effect, zinc.

Introduction

Nutrient interaction very frequently modifies the availability of native as well as applied nutrients. In a highly developed agriculture, large increases in yield potential derives from various kinds of interactions namely between plant nutrients, nutrients and cultural practices etc. Therefore, an interaction of plant nutrients as well as interaction of nutrients with different soil, water and other management practices drastically modify the availability of nutrients in soils and hence reflects on crop production². Rice is commonly grown under puddled submerged soil condition where zinc becomes a limiting element. So, interactions of nutrients like N and K with Zn may moderate or enhance the availability of Zn in submerged soil. Keeping these in view, the present investigation was undertaken to study the interaction effect between K and Zn on the available K and cationic micronutrients including Zn in submerged soil.

Results and discussion

Exchangeable potassium :

The results (Table 2) revealed that the available potassium content has been found to be significantly influenced by different treatments over control. The amount of exchangeable K has been found to be increased from 14 to 42 days of incubation and thereafter, the amount of the same decreased irrespective of treatments throughout 90 days of incubation. The significant decrease in the amount of exchangeable K was observed after 42 days of incubation and continued upto 90 days (146.34 mg kg⁻¹) which was about 22.65% lower than that of the highest value (189.20 mg kg⁻¹) in the T₆ treatment where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 5 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied togetherly at 42 days of incubation. The other higher values of exchangeable K was observed in the treatment T₃ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + no application of Zn were applied (185.39 mg kg⁻¹

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the initial soil

Soil properties	Values
Mechanical composition (%)	
Clay (%)	45
Clay + Silt (%)	55
Texture	Clayey loam
pH	7.03
EC (dSm ⁻¹)	0.16
Organic C (g kg ⁻¹)	0.56
Available N (kg ha ⁻¹)	239.54
Available P (kg ha ⁻¹)	53.01
Available K (kg ha ⁻¹)	127.59
DTPA-extractable Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	10.53
DTPA-extractable Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	9.7
DTPA-extractable Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.72
DTPA-extractable Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	2.29

ascribed by the formation of Fe-K insoluble complex under submerged condition¹.

DTPA-extractable Zn :

The results (Table 3) showed that the amount of DTPA-extractable Zn increased initially and thereafter, the amount of the same decreased with the progress of submergence. Such changes might be due to the effect of soil submergence resulting Zn unavailable. The highest amount of DTPA extractable Zn was found in the treatment T₉ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied combinedly (10.18 mg kg⁻¹) at 14 days of incubation which was closely followed by the treatment T₈ where, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were both applied (9.09 mg kg⁻¹). The interaction between Zn and K at their

Table 2. Interaction effect between K and Zn on the periodic changes in extractable K content (mg kg⁻¹) in submerged soil

Treatments	Days of incubation					
	14	28	42	63	84	90
T ₁ – K ₀ Zn ₀ – Control, No application of Zn and K	109.87	92.25	86.74	73.91	62.98	55.18
T ₂ – K ₁ Zn ₀ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No Application of Zn	149.56	168.22	176.58	151.23	136.79	128.52
T ₃ – K ₂ Zn ₀ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No Application of Zn	163.85	177.59	185.39	170.52	153.98	140.21
T ₄ – K ₀ Zn ₁ – No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	147.28	168.86	176.42	153.47	137.11	126.58
T ₅ – K ₁ Zn ₁ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	154.27	174.85	177.03	155.47	142.53	137.96
T ₆ – K ₂ Zn ₁ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	166.36	180.58	189.2	173.28	159.2	146.34
T ₇ – K ₀ Zn ₂ – No application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	144.21	165.48	172.49	152.24	133.95	122.43
T ₈ – K ₁ Zn ₂ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	151.79	169.2	174.11	153.29	139.21	132.02
T ₉ – K ₂ Zn ₂ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	161.22	176.26	183.77	166.86	152.25	139.25
SEm	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01
CD (P = 0.05)	0.17	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.03

soil) and treatment T₉ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied combinedly (183.77 mg kg⁻¹). Such initial increase of K might be due to the positive interaction between potassium and zinc fertilizer as well as soil submergence resulting an increase in K either from the release of native soil or applied potassic fertilizer, while decrease of the same at the later period of submergence might be

highest levels has been found to be positive and significant with respect to initial enhancement of Zn. The overall results suggested a significant decrease in the amount of DTPA-extractable Zn in submerged soil and such decrease was recorded at the later period of submergence. However, such decrease in the amount of DTPA extractable Zn at the later period of submergence might be due to formation of franklinite type of mineral, Zn-Fe₂O₄¹.

Table 3. Interaction effect between K and Zn on the periodic changes in DTPA extractable Zn content (mg kg⁻¹) in submerged soil

Treatments	Days of incubation													
	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	90	
T ₁ - K ₀ Zn ₀ - Control, No application of Zn and K	2.02	1.78	1.69	1.40	1.31	1.22	0.98	0.74	0.65	0.56	0.44	0.38	0.31	
T ₂ - K ₁ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn	3.22	3.66	3.50	3.43	3.31	3.08	2.95	2.66	2.54	2.49	2.35	2.24	2.16	
T ₃ - K ₂ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn	2.95	5.63	5.36	5.12	4.98	4.70	4.49	4.17	3.87	3.59	3.47	3.36	3.19	
T ₄ - K ₀ Zn ₁ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	3.96	6.12	5.79	5.64	5.22	5.03	4.76	4.50	4.26	3.98	3.80	3.62	3.56	
T ₅ - K ₁ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	5.25	6.74	6.23	6.06	5.70	5.41	5.21	4.83	4.52	4.30	4.03	3.89	3.76	
T ₆ - K ₂ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	7.00	7.37	7.09	6.77	6.61	6.25	6.02	5.65	5.34	5.03	4.75	4.44	4.21	
T ₇ - K ₀ Zn ₂ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	7.87	8.26	7.75	7.50	7.34	7.09	6.86	6.58	6.20	5.86	5.63	5.29	4.95	
T ₈ - K ₁ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	8.69	9.09	8.78	8.46	8.23	8.02	7.61	7.26	6.81	6.39	6.12	5.75	5.43	
T ₉ - K ₂ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	9.73	10.18	9.72	9.38	9.12	8.78	8.49	8.10	7.63	7.23	6.96	6.54	6.25	
SEm	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	
CD (P = 0.05)	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	

Table 4. Interaction effect between K and Zn on the periodic changes in DTPA extractable Cu content (mg kg^{-1}) in submerged soil

Treatments	Days of incubation												
	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	90
T ₁ - K ₀ Zn ₀ - Control, No application of Zn and K	1.75	1.69	1.58	1.44	1.22	0.90	0.77	0.61	0.50	0.45	0.32	0.19	0.10
T ₂ - K ₁ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn	1.73	1.82	1.87	1.91	1.70	1.65	1.62	1.41	1.13	0.92	0.81	0.58	0.45
T ₃ - K ₂ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn	1.74	1.87	1.89	2.02	1.95	1.80	1.31	1.16	1.08	0.94	0.86	0.73	0.56
T ₄ - K ₀ Zn ₁ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	1.78	1.98	2.01	2.13	2.09	1.92	1.75	1.60	1.51	1.34	1.05	0.87	0.68
T ₅ - K ₁ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	1.81	2.02	2.07	2.16	2.11	2.01	1.82	2.78	1.69	1.55	1.41	1.16	0.89
T ₆ - K ₂ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	1.87	2.05	2.14	2.26	2.18	2.03	1.94	2.83	2.71	1.66	1.58	1.33	1.16
T ₇ - K ₀ Zn ₂ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	1.95	2.09	2.17	2.35	2.27	2.10	2.03	1.86	1.81	1.75	1.64	1.52	1.35
T ₈ - K ₁ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	2.02	2.14	2.19	2.49	2.36	2.15	2.05	1.94	1.82	1.80	1.71	1.67	1.49
T ₉ - K ₂ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	2.10	2.21	2.30	2.64	2.49	2.34	2.20	2.12	1.90	1.84	1.83	1.78	1.61
SEM	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02
CD (P = 0.05)	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04

Table 5. Interaction effect between K and Zn on the periodic changes in DTPA extractable Mn content (mg kg⁻¹) in submerged soil

Treatments	Days of incubation													
	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	90	
T ₁ – K ₀ Zn ₀ – Control, No application of Zn and K	21.32	24.65	29.49	36.26	43.62	51.81	44.52	43.38	39.09	35.74	29.03	24.62	18.58	
T ₂ – K ₁ Zn ₀ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No applicatiion of Zn	16.75	19.38	23.63	28.37	32.05	41.41	37.67	33.93	30.65	24.99	20.68	16.91	13.03	
T ₃ – K ₂ Zn ₀ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn	20.29	25.78	31.01	37.92	44.81	51.43	46.74	42.63	39.32	36.08	32.40	27.87	21.13	
T ₄ – K ₀ Zn ₁ – No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	20.13	27.46	32.55	39.95	46.50	50.77	48.73	46.26	43.47	39.73	37.06	32.60	27.39	
T ₅ – K ₁ Zn ₁ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	22.04	30.60	34.37	41.29	48.24	54.78	51.16	48.29	45.07	42.13	39.30	35.54	33.29	
T ₆ – K ₂ Zn ₁ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	26.63	36.80	38.94	42.88	49.87	56.77	51.80	48.68	46.91	43.53	41.15	38.13	35.05	
T ₇ – K ₀ Zn ₂ – No Application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	25.70	37.11	40.40	44.35	51.93	58.93	55.86	51.22	48.13	45.88	42.88	39.69	37.09	
T ₈ – K ₁ Zn ₂ – Application of K @ 30 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	29.43	41.33	43.26	47.36	54.90	61.86	57.47	54.94	52.73	49.94	46.11	41.60	37.26	
T ₉ – K ₂ Zn ₂ – Application of K @ 60 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg ⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA	33.62	47.64	49.43	51.30	57.39	64.94	59.31	56.27	55.87	52.89	50.12	45.88	42.71	
SEM	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	
CD (P = 0.05)	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.05	

Table 6. Interaction effect between K and Zn on the periodic changes in DTPA extractable Fe content (mg kg^{-1}) in submerged soil

Treatments	Days of incubation												
	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	90
T ₁ - K ₀ Zn ₀ - Control, No application of Zn and K	39.57	40.66	44.88	51.05	56.27	62.68	51.70	49.16	44.82	43.18	39.14	34.81	31.25
T ₂ - K ₁ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + No application of Zn	44.36	51.56	60.30	66.50	77.97	81.21	71.10	61.92	51.14	47.75	44.81	42.06	36.70
T ₃ - K ₂ Zn ₀ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + No application of Zn	51.43	68.50	73.00	78.00	86.21	91.95	81.88	75.60	61.43	51.25	48.61	45.56	44.44
T ₄ - K ₀ Zn ₁ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	56.62	78.02	89.30	95.26	104.95	111.97	101.66	95.02	86.43	77.31	66.19	57.99	49.96
T ₅ - K ₁ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	59.85	81.38	104.94	112.82	118.66	121.01	112.13	110.21	101.97	94.62	83.36	66.50	60.96
T ₆ - K ₂ Zn ₁ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	63.33	82.62	110.49	118.18	120.50	126.05	118.80	119.92	111.28	104.12	99.45	88.93	81.10
T ₇ - K ₀ Zn ₂ - No application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	73.93	89.42	112.81	121.49	128.00	131.70	120.89	116.52	112.11	105.53	101.17	97.39	90.63
T ₈ - K ₀ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	77.24	104.40	118.94	123.44	136.94	148.18	128.45	117.59	113.74	108.09	104.79	100.82	96.93
T ₉ - K ₂ Zn ₂ - Application of K @ 60 mg kg^{-1} soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg^{-1} soil as Zn-EOTA	84.48	107.19	122.55	127.92	133.27	152.94	143.41	125.13	119.13	111.53	105.55	103.96	101.29
SEm	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.03
CD (P = 0.05)	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.06

DTPA-extractable Cu :

The results (Table 4) showed that the amount of DTPA-extractable Cu increased initially and then consistent decrease was observed with the progress of submergence. The possible explanation for the increase in the concentration of Cu in submerged soils initially might be due to the partly release of Cu from the coated hydroxides of Fe^{3+} and Mn^{4+} resulting from the reduction of soil and also partly for the production of soluble Cu-organic chelates thus increasing its solubility¹. The highest amount of DTPA extractable Cu was found in the treatment T₉ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied combinedly (2.64 mg kg⁻¹) at 28 days of incubation which was closely followed by the treatment T₈ where, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were both applied (2.49 mg kg⁻¹) and treatment T₇ where, no K + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA was applied (2.35 mg kg⁻¹). The interaction between Zn and K at their highest levels had been found to be positive and significant with respect to initial enhancement of Cu. However, the overall results suggested a significant decrease in the amount of DTPA extractable Cu in submerged soil with progress of incubation period after 28 days of submergence till 90 days. The decrease might be attributed to the microbial immobilization and also due to antagonistic effect of Cu with increased concentrations of iron, manganese and phosphorus forming insoluble copper complexes in soils¹.

DTPA-extractable Mn :

The results (Table 5) showed that the amount of DTPA-extractable Mn increased initially and then gradual decrease was observed with the progress of submergence. Such changes might be due to the effect of soil submergence rendering Mn unavailable at the later stages of submergence. The highest amount of DTPA extractable Mn was recorded in the treatment T₉ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied combinedly (64.94 mg kg⁻¹) at 42 days of incubation which was closely followed by the treatment T₈ where, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were both applied togetherly (61.86 mg kg⁻¹) and treatment T₇ where, no K + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA was applied (58.93 mg kg⁻¹). The interaction between Zn and K at their highest levels has

been found to be positive and significant with respect to initial enhancement of Mn. The initial increase in the concentration of Mn^{2+} might be due to the reduction of Mn^{4+} to Mn^{2+} resulting from the submergence and the decrease of the same at the later stages of submergence might be due to the precipitation of Mn^{2+} as MnCO_3 and $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ in the soil solution¹.

DTPA-extractable Fe :

The results (Table 6) showed that the amount of DTPA-extractable Fe increased initially and then consistent decrease was observed towards the later period of submergence. Such changes might be due to soil submergence causing reduction of iron accompanied by the increase in its solubility. The concentration of ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) increased initially to some peak value and thereafter, decreased gradually with the period of soil submergence. The initial increase in concentration of Fe^{2+} on soil submergence was recorded by the reduction of insoluble $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ to soluble Fe^{2+} (Das, 2011). However the amount of DTPA extractable Fe decreased gradually after 42 days of incubation. The highest amount of DTPA extractable Fe was found in the treatment T₉ where, K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were applied combinedly (152.94 mg kg⁻¹) at 42 days of incubation which was closely followed by the treatment T₈ where, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA were both applied (148.18 mg kg⁻¹) and treatment T₇ where, no K + Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA was applied (131.7 mg kg⁻¹). The results of the present study also find support with the findings of Verma and Tripathi³ who reported that Fe concentration in soil increases with an increasing levels of applied zinc. However, the amount gradually decreased with the progress of incubation period which might be due to the formation of insoluble iron compounds¹.

Experimental

Laboratory experiment was conducted in an aeric haplaquept (Sub-Divisional Adaptive Research Farm, Kandi, Murshidabad) at the Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Institute of Agricultural Science, University of Calcutta, Kolkata to study the interaction effect between K and Zn with the following treatments replicated thrice in a completely randomized design (CRD). The initial physico-chemical properties of

the soil (Table 1) namely pH, Organic Carbon, exchangeable K was determined by the method described by Jackson⁴. The DTPA extractable Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn were extracted by following the method described by Lindsay and Norvell⁶ and determined with the help of atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, Perkin-Elmer model AAAnalyst 100). The nine different treatments which were replicated thrice are being described below :

T₁ – Control, Soil only, No application of Zn and K

T₂ – Soil + Application of K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn

T₃ – Soil + Application of K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + No application of Zn

T₄ – Soil + No application of K + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

T₅ – Soil + Application of K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

T₆ – Soil + Application of K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 5 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

T₇ – Soil + No application of K + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

T₈ – Soil + Application of K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

T₉ – Soil + Application of K @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ soil as MOP + Application of Zn @ 10 mg kg⁻¹ soil as Zn-EDTA

The treated soils were incubated at ambient conditions in the laboratory. Continuous submergence was

maintained throughout the incubation period at a depth of 3.0 ± 0.5 cm by periodic addition of de-ionised water. The sets of plastic container were arranged for 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, 42, 49, 56, 63, 70, 77, 84 and 90 days of incubation. The derived data was interpreted statistically by the method described by Fishers⁵.

Conclusion

The overall results suggest that the interaction effect between potassium and zinc has been found to be positive with respect to their availability in soils. The results further revealed that the lower level of Zn has been proved superior on the availability of K while that of the highest level of K was proved beneficial for the availability of cationic micronutrients in soils.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi under Inspire Program Scheme in the form of fellowship and annual contingency to the first author.

References

1. D. K. Das, "Introductory Soil Science", Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, 2011, **3**, pp. 464-493.
2. D. K. Das, "Micronutrients : Their Behaviour in Soils and Plants", Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, 2007.
3. T. S. Verma and B. R. Tripathi, *Plant and Soil*, 1983, **1**, 107.
4. M. L. Jackson, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice Hall of India Private Limited, New Delhi, 1973.
5. R. A. Fisher, "The Design of Experiment", Hoffman Publication Company Inc., New York, 1960.
6. W. L. Lindsay and W. A. Norvell, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1978, **42**, 421.